

Thinking Styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty at Davao City Jail

Enrique T. Umusig Jr.¹, CaliarKlent Jan T. Calimpong², Rufa Mae I. Gordo³, Irish P. Bandolos⁴

¹(College of Criminal Justice/ University of Mindanao,Philippines)

²(College of Criminal Justice/ University of Mindanao,Philippines)

³(College of Criminal Justice/ University of Mindanao,Philippines)

⁴(College of Criminal Justice/ University of Mindanao,Philippines)

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the extent of the thinking styles of persons deprived of liberty at the Davao City Jail. The researchers want to know the prevalent thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail. Moreover, the study sought to determine the manifestation of criminal thinking style in terms of mollification, cutoff, entitlement, power orientation, sentimentality, super optimism, cognitive indolence, and discontinuity. The data of this study came from N-299 Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail. They were collected using a random sampling technique to ensure they answered the questions honestly. The Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles (PICTS), a survey questionnaire from Walter and Kaufman (1995), was the research tool employed in the study. Through the use of a validated questionnaire, the mean and the standard deviation are determined. The study found that super optimism is prevalent among all criminal thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail. Further, the researcher recommends that jail and correctional institutions ensure that their facilities have a psychologist who will provide and oversee programs to lower recidivism rates and offer regular counseling to all prisoners.

KEYWORDS –thinking style, jail, prison, Deprived of Liberty (PDLs, quantitative descriptive research, criminology, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Offenders' thinking style has been a vital indicator of criminal behavior for quite some time. Still, relatively few studies have examined the connection between criminal thinking patterns and personality in offenders. (Jha & Sharma, 2020). By the twenty-first century, criminologists looked to various factors to explain why a person would commit crimes. For instance, Ward et al. (2019) included biological, psychological, sociological, and cultural elements from several disciplines to understand criminal behavior. Additionally, it is crucial to remember that decision-making, which includes intellectual and emotional factors, significantly impacts human behavior and shows that such factors may affect criminal behavior (Campello et al., 2016). In this way, it is vital to recognize and investigate a local sample's measurement, precursors, and results of criminal thinking patterns. By studying the common thinking styles of the offenders, we can innovate some deterrence and lessen the crimes committed. The key to understanding lawbreakers is to know the fundamental attributes of all criminal behaviors rather than their specific acts (Bonta & Andrews, 2017). Prosocial conduct and criminal thinking appear mutually exclusive (MartVilar et al., 2019).

Llorca et al. (2016), the commission of aggressive conduct, suggests that the existence of one of these variables tends to be influenced by the presence of the other. According to Walters (2017), improving prosocial abilities and thinking decreases antisocial behavior in Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), which affects criminal thinking. It is necessary to conduct this research to look at what 2 are currently known factors that connect with and foresee criminal thinking styles. Walters (2012) showed that criminal thinking, as estimated by

the PICTS, is altogether connected with recidivism. Not all people with criminal conduct are managed in the state or government therapeutic settings. By cutting down the number of funds taxpayers spend incarcerating offenders, creative and proper sentencing would benefit society (Walters, 2016).

This study wants to find the prevalent thinking styles among the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) inside the jail. It is intriguing to assess offenders. By participating in forensic interviews or interrogations, the perpetrator's thought process can be clearly understood, including how they rationalize their actions and whether they accept or reject responsibility (Johnson, 2016). They are less likely to harm others if they adhere to the principle of respect. Criminal thinking literature likewise suggests that criminal thinking predicts recidivism (Walters, 2012; Walters & Lowenkamp, 2016). All the more explicitly, Walters (2012) observed that overall lawbreaker thinking anticipated recidivism far over a person's criminal history and age. Megreya (2015) researched the thinking style between emotional intelligence and criminal behavior using samples of inmates and non-inmates. The findings of this study, non-offenders had higher levels of emotional intelligence than offenders.

Additionally, emotional intelligence declined in proportion to how serious the crime was, being higher for offenses like robbery and lower for offenses like murder. Based on the examinations imply that individuals indicted for violent offenses present with more comprehensive chronicles of violence than people sentenced for robbery. It has been noted that the prevalence of psychopathic thinking may be predicted in a sample of violent criminals (Farrington & Lambert, 1994; Delfin et al., 2018). As of now, the most that can be said is that violent crime embodies elements of both specialization and versatility. Indeed, even with this, a few delimiting factors, like the beginning time, decide the general heterogeneity in the offending pattern.

Criminal thinking is a risk component of criminal conduct that can be focused on to diminish recidivism (Bonta & Andrews, 2017). If law enforcement were to devise better approaches for recognizing and capturing lawbreakers consistently, we would have no issues; wrongdoing would be a relic of times. The issue is that criminals are additionally contriving better approaches to perpetrate crime, making a rivalry of sorts. Ilan (2019) also recognized that criminal activity and efforts to regulate it are artifacts of civilization. The same culture that decides what constitutes a crime also produces and regulates these behaviors. Several circumstances can influence criminal thinking. If offenders' criminal mindset is not challenged and transformed, they are likely to re-offend. One research by the National Institute of Justice tracked 404,638 convicts in 30 states. Researchers discovered that 56.7 percent of inmates were re-arrested within the first year after being released from jail, and 76.6 percent were re-arrested within the first five years (National Institute of Justice, 2014) because of the significant risk of recidivism. An offender must be given proper way of treatment when serving his sentence.

This study is anchored on General strain theory (GST). It gives an extraordinary clarification of crime and delinquency. As opposed to controlling and learning theories, GST centers expressly around pessimistic treatment by 4 others and is the central theory of crime and misconduct to feature the role of negative emotions in the etiology of culpability. As indicated by GST, the experience of strain or stress will, in general, create pessimistic feelings like resentment, dissatisfaction, melancholy, and depression. These pessimistic feelings and thinking, thus, are said to create pressures for remedial activity, with wrongdoing or delinquency being one potential reaction (Brezina, 2017). Moreover, people who are under strain or stress frequently feel agitated and occasionally turn to crime as a coping mechanism. The basic tenet of GST is this straightforward notion, while the theory goes on to develop it in several ways. For example, GST outlines the main strain categories, identifies the strains that are most likely to result in crime, explains why these strains result in crime, and explains why only a tiny percentage of stressed-out people turn to criminal coping. The GST also offers ideas for crime prevention and explains offending throughout a person's life and the disparities in crime between groups. These GST facets are thoroughly discussed in this chapter (Agnew & Brezina, 2019). It is simple to recognize how GST applies to misconduct in prison. Offenders also encounter many stressful and negative experiences, all likely to cause a range of emotions that could eventually lead to misconduct while institutionalized. On the presumption of innocence, detainees who have not been tried are separated from those who have been found guilty (Vienna, 2018).

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 below shows the primary and moderating variables. The single-headed arrow pointing to the primary variable (criminal thinking styles) indicates an influence of the moderator variable (profile 5 of the respondents) or its indicators, namely age, sex, criminal offense, and marital status, on the primary variable. The study's primary variable is inmates' criminal thinking styles with its indicators: mollification pertains to a thinking style in which an individual blames someone or something else, just like social injustice, for their actions or downplays the severity of the behavior and its effects. This allows the person to avoid taking responsibility for their choices and the repercussions of those choices.

Cutoff refers to a cognitive process in which an individual can use a strategy, such as a phrase of bad words or mental image, to stop these feelings and any other internal events like thoughts about consequences that might prevent them from committing the crime.

An attitude of ownership, privilege, and misidentifying goals and needs characterizes entitlement. It enables individuals to reject or evade established standards that apply to them and control and escape pain by claiming anything they desire.

Power orientation, containing zero state and power push, is evident when the person's "outward shows of hostility" capacity to "control and control others."

Sentimentality pertains to a mental tendency that allows an offender to emphasize they are positive traits by focusing on their good actions while ignoring the consequences of their unlawful behavior to be viewed as a good person. Super optimism refers to an offender with erroneous self-judgments of personal characteristics and erroneous perceptions of his or her ability to escape the repercussions of criminal action.

Cognitive indolence, which means "lazy thinking, short-cut problem solutions, and uncritical acceptance of personal ideas and plans," are all characteristics of cognitive indolence. Finally, discontinuity is related to 6 cognitive styles in which the offender lacks self-control or avoids commitment. This involves being inconsistent in carrying out plans or goals, which obstructs the offender's capacity to make long-term improvements, even when the offender desires them.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

This study aims to determine the extent of the thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail. Moreover, the study sought to determine the level of criminal thinking style in terms of mollification, cutoff, entitlement, power orientation, sentimentality, super optimism, cognitive indolence, and discontinuity. This will also establish the significant difference in the criminal thinking style when the respondents are grouped according to age, sex, criminal offense, and marital status. The hypothesis revealed no significant difference in the level of thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail when the respondents were grouped under age, sex, criminal offense, and marital status in a 0.05 margin of error. The researchers thoroughly examined and used all approaches needed to understand the differences in Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) thinking styles to develop possible solutions and applications for the problem. This study will focus on the criminal thinking styles that offenders commonly have. Differences in the demographic profile may influence their thinking styles, such as age, sex, criminal offense, and marital status.

The study is significant to the law enforcers, the contents of the study would help them monitor the criminal thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL). This study would give law enforcers some idea of how to understand the offenders they are taking into custody. It would also help them create a strategy or innovate policies to deter those offenders adequately. This research would show the prevalent indicators of criminal thinking, and law enforcers can look at this to provide some practical solutions. Further, correctional institution the results of this study would help raise the officials' awareness about the thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty. This study would allow them to determine the prevalent criminal thinking styles of the offenders. Thanks to this study, they would be able to identify the typical criminal thought patterns of the offenders. This would also help them build policies on how to deal with people being denied their freedoms, as well as security measures to safeguard the security of all inhabitants. Furthermore, the students can have an overview of the potential characteristics of an individual who might become an offender. This would also give them an idea to be cautious and protect themselves in times of crisis. For future researchers, this would give them an in-depth understanding of the thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail. The study's respondents are mostly inmates with drug-related cases; this would encourage them to provide another type of criminal offense of an offender to look for more information about their thinking style. For instance, future researchers can dig deeper into the criminal thinking styles of criminal offenders convicted of other offenses.

II. METHODS

The researcher presents the research design, the respondents, the sampling design, the research instrument, the data-gathering procedure, and the statistical tools used in the study.

Research Subjects

The researcher used the stratified random sampling technique to determine the suitable respondents. It allows all the males and females to answer the research questions voluntarily. The respondents in the Davao City Jail were identified through a stratified random sampling technique to ensure that anyone had a chance of being selected. In stratified random sampling, the strata are formed based on the shared characteristics of a minimum of 300 offenders. However, suddenly, 1 of the respondents backed out and did not answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents in the Davao City Jail were identified through a random sampling technique to ensure they answered the questions honestly. It explains the situation where each component of the population has an equal chance of getting chosen for the sample (Shin, 2020). The researchers exercised their judgment in the choice and included those items in the sample. Moreover, the study commenced at Davao City Jail between October and September 2022.

Research Instruments

The research instrument used in the study is a survey questionnaire called The Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles (PICTS) from Walter & Kaufman (1995). The existing questionnaire contains 80 questions supported by eight indicators explicitly formulated to assess the typical level of each thinking style indicator. This is a structured questionnaire designed to help understand individual thinking and behavior. In line with this, the respondent's personality perspective was collected through this instrument to determine a criminal's most common thinking styles. The questions were designed to evaluate the respondent's thinking style. Five with a mean range of 4.20-5.00 is very high, meaning the thinking style among respondents greatly reflects. The rating of four with a mean score of 3.40-4.19 is high, meaning the Thinking Style among respondents is reflected. Further, a rating of three with a mean of 2.60-3.39 is moderate, meaning that the thinking style among respondents somewhat reflects this. Furthermore, the rating of two with a range of mean 1.80-2.59 is low, which means that the thinking style among respondents almost does not reflect. Lastly, the rating of one with a range of 1.00-1.79 is meager, which means that the thinking style among respondents did not reflect.

Research Design and Procedure

In this research study, we used a descriptive survey method. This is because descriptive survey methods can be used to use and systematically describe the traits and phenomena. As per Sandra Siedlecki (2020), a descriptive study means to depict events, people, or conditions by concentrating on them immediately of their unique circumstances. She added that this approach could investigate a single variable, view the characteristics of the populace, and recognize happening issues. Further, Akhtar (2016) expressed that this approach includes depicting a peculiarity as it exists, concentrating on a current circumstance at the end of the day. These requirements recognize and get essential data on the attributes of a specific issue, like a group of people. To determine the thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at the Davao City Jail, it would look at and describe the level of criminal thinking styles when analyzed in terms of gender, age, criminal offense, and marital status. The research instrument used in the study is a questionnaire from Walter and Kaufman (1995). The existing questionnaire contains 80 questions supported by eight indicators explicitly formulated to assess the expected level of each thinking style indicator. In the end, researchers are motivated to know the most prevalent criminal thinking styles among the offenders.

During the data collection process, the researchers created a letter of approval indicating the desire to collect data outside the university. The letter, which has the dean's signature, was addressed to the Jail Chief Superintendent of the Davao City Jail to get permission to conduct the study. The researchers used an adapted questionnaire called the Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles (PICTS) from Walter & Kaufman (1995). In order to safeguard and protect the rights of the respondents, the researchers allowed subject-matter experts to review the survey questions before they were administered. In addition, since we are considering the safety procedures, the survey questionnaires were distributed in hard copy papers. When the researcher conducted the survey, the Davao City Jail inmates' total population was 6,647 initially. The male dormitory has a total of five thousand nine hundred and ninety-eight. At the same time, six hundred forty-nine offenders were in the female dormitory. Then, the researchers retrieved and collected all the answered questionnaires and prepared them for data analysis. After retrieving questionnaires, they tallied and tabled the data conducted. The data should be analyzed and interpreted with the help of different statistical tools; the result served as the researchers' basis for formulating their discussion recommendation and conclusion.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data: Mean was used to determine the level of criminal thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) in terms of Mollification, Cutoff, Entitlement, Power Orientation, Super optimism, Sentimentality, Cognitive Indolence, and Discontinuity. Then, a T-test was used to determine the thinking styles of offenders in terms of gender, age, criminal offense, and marital status. Standard deviation measures how close the scores are centered on the mean score (Perumal, 2012). This tool was used to decide how close the average scores of the students' demographic profiles were to the

overall mean. While Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is a tool used to compare the means and variance of more than two groups. It is a tool used to determine the level of criminal thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) when analyzed in terms of their demographic (Kim, 2014)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the researcher interprets and presents the findings from the collected data. Following is a presentation and arrangement of the tables: (1) the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following classification: gender, age, criminal offense, and marital status; (2) the level of manifestation of criminal thinking styles of Davao City Jail Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) (3) significance of difference in criminal thinking styles per demographic profile. To further discuss the result, researchers tried to find some related results concerning the study. The researcher also reviewed related literature and studies to support the study's findings.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 displays the demographic distribution of Davao City Jail Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) regarding gender, age, criminal offense, and marital status. The data shows that most respondents are female (n = 150). The majority bracket of ages is tied between twenty-eight to thirty-two years old and thirty-three to thirty-seven years old (n = 70). Among the five categories of criminal offenses committed by the offenders at the Davao City Jail, mainly under the offense of drug-related crimes with a total frequency of (n = 252). Lastly, the majority marital status among the four categories of the respondents is single, with a total of (n=206).

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Davao City Jail Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL)

Profile	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	149	49.8
Female	150	50.2
Age		
18–22 years old	34	11.4
23–27 years old	60	20.1
28–32 years old	70	23.4
33–37 years old	70	23.4
38 – 42 years old	37	12.4
Above 42 years old	28	9.4
Criminal Offense		
Crime Against Person	17	5.7
Crime Against Properties Drug-Related Crimes	17	5.7
Fraud Cases	252	84.3
Others	10	3.3
	3	1.0
Marital Status		
Single	206	68.9
Married	75	25.1
Widowed	6	2.0
Separated	12	4.0

Level of Manifestation of Criminal Thinking Styles

As shown in Table 2, super optimism obtained the highest mean of 3.19 (SD=0.86), the majority of criminal thinking styles. This means the respondents have moderate criminal thinking styles regarding super

optimism. Then, cutoff and sentimentality thinking styles obtained almost the same mean of 2.98 (SD=0.98) and a mean of 2.95 (SD=0.71) and interpreted that the respondents have a moderate level of criminal thinking styles in terms of cutoff and sentimentality. Lastly, power orientation got a mean of 2.28 (SD=0.93), the lowest manifestation of criminal thinking styles. This means that the respondents have low criminal thinking styles regarding power orientation. In the event of failure, super optimism gives one a sense of external control. This means that a person considers the failure a circumstance where they are not at fault and places the blame on other factors, regardless of whether they believe the situation to be an exercise or a purpose. Overestimating the likelihood of resisting unpleasant things is a tendency repercussion of criminal activity. Based on the study by Therapon University (2015), offenders utilize super optimism to persuade themselves that they do not need to put any effort into making things work out well. The inmates' perception of how easily things will come together for them will be imprinted. Criminals who think this way do not understand the link between hard work and achievement. This result will support the study made by Palmer and Hollin (2012); when it comes to predicting the outcome after release, the Cut-off scale performed best for male criminals, while the sentimentality scale performed best for female offenders.

Based on the study of "Kent Academic Repository" (2015), it is an aggressive tactic used to exert influence over others in power orientation, which may help to explain why these particular criminal offenses are so life-destroying. It refers to the aggressive control of people and situations and is more pronounced in murderers (Megreya et al., 2015). This statement supports our result because most of our respondents are convicted of drug-related crimes, which is why this thinking style got the lowest manifestation. Therefore, the power orientation thinking style is weak for inmates with drug-related cases.

Table 2 Level of Manifestation of Criminal Thinking Styles of Davao City Jail Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL)

Criminal Thinking Style	Mean	SD
Mollification	2.89	.79
Cutoff	2.98	.98
Entitlement	2.68	.95
Power Orientation	2.28	.93
Sentimentality	2.95	.71
Super optimism	3.19	.86
Cognitive Indolence	2.74	.84
Discontinuity	2.32	.93

Significance of Difference in Criminal Thinking Styles

In terms of the discontinuity thinking style, there is a significant difference concerning gender ($t = -2.063$, $p = .040$), criminal offense ($f = 2.146$, $p = .075$), and marital status ($f = 3.239$, $p = .023$). Since the p-values are less than 0.05, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference in the criminal thinking style concerning the participant's gender, criminal offense, and marital status. Regarding the power orientation thinking style, there is a significant difference between gender ($t = 2.197$, $p = .029$) and age ($f = 2.500$, $p = .031$). Since the p-values are less than 0.05, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference in the criminal thinking style concerning the participant's gender and age.

For cognitive indolence thinking style, there is a significant difference concerning gender ($t = 7.728$, $p = .000$) and criminal offense ($f = 2.590$, $p = .037$). Since the p-values are less than 0.05, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference in the criminal thinking style for the participant's gender and criminal offense. Lastly, most criminal thinking styles have significant differences concerning gender. Such as mollification ($t = 8.687$, $p = .000$), cutoff ($t = 7.894$, $p = .000$), entitlement ($t = 8.879$,

p=.000), sentimentality (t=-2.618, p=.009), and super optimism (t=10.341, p=.000). Since all of the p-values are less than 0.05, then there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

In American male prisoners, discontinuity strongly predicts recidivism (Walters,2014). The result is supported by the study by Zana Vrucinic (2019); according to their statistics, respondents' criminal thinking styles change depending on how violent the criminal offense is. Inmates who committed non- violent crimes scored higher in discontinuity than those who committed serious crimes. This mistake is among the most significant ones perpetuating the criminal lifestyle and hinders targeted attention on the issues that have caused criminal behavior. This cognitive mistake causes changes in both thinking and actual conduct (Enke & Gneezy, 2021). The cited writers emphasize that discontinuity is a "glue" to bind cognitive mistakes. Furthermore, the implication of our result opposed the study conducted by Palmer (2014), where they found no significant difference in power orientation between young and adult offenders.

Cognitive indolence describes the unobservant, quickly bored, and lazy features of the criminal's mental state at that time. Criminals look for shortcuts to accomplish their aims and persuade themselves that the shortcut is the best way to do it (Lauren Pyle, 2016). This result is similar to the study of Zana Vrucinic (2019), whose survey showed that older offenders are more inclined to cognitive indolence than younger offenders. Also, prisoners who are a father who practices emotional maltreatment of their children can sign a high cognitive indolence pattern of thinking (Malek Alkhutaba, 2018).The result of the study is similar to the work of Deric Kenne (2010); males and females had different patterns of thinking error, and there was a noticeable gender difference in the mollification of thinking error. Compared to female offenders, male offenders showed much higher levels of mollification thinking error. It would follow that male offenders are more inclined than female offenders to put the blame for and justify their unlawful behavior on others.It also supports the study conducted by Wilson et al. (2014). Men in the current jail sample had relatively high Cutoff scores, which point to emotional instability and impulsive problems. People who score this thinking style clinically higher have been defined as "having a hot temper with a tendency to retain a maintain it approach to problem-solving" (Morgan et al., 2010, p. 331).

Analogous to the results of the study conducted by Tangney et al. (2012), they also found that males are more inclined to the notions of entitlement than females. However, Vaske et al. (2016) obtained a different result where they found no significant difference in entitlement regarding gender.It would also define the work of Deric Kenne (2014); females are more susceptible than males to falling victim to the "sentimentality" thinking error. Males were more likely than females to place blame for their actions on outside forces. Both genders who were jailed for domestic violence shared this trait. It suggests that while engaging in criminal behavior had negative consequences, most female offenders still believed they were pleasant individuals.According to a study by Palmer and Hollin (2012), the sentimentality scale fared best for female criminals. This finding validates that result, which explains that doing good deeds can undo the damage caused by a criminal lifestyle.

Table 3 Significance of Difference in Criminal Thinking Styles per Demographic Profile

Criminal Thinking Style	Gender		Age		Criminal Offense		Marital Status	
	t-value	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value
Cutoff	7.894	.000	1.18 2	.318	1.62 1	.169	1.34 3	.261
Entitlement	8.879	.000	.894	.485	2.29 8	.059	.375	.771

Power Orientation	2.197	.029	2.500	.031	3.516	.008	1.933	.124
Sentimentality	-2.618	.009	1.290	.268	1.222	.302	1.990	.116
Superoptimism	10.341	.000	1.301	.263	1.901	.110	.531	.661
Cognitive Indolence	7.728	.000	1.326	.253	2.590	.037	2.387	.069
Discontinuity	-2.063	.040	1.448	.207	2.146	.075	3.239	.023

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the study reveals that super optimism is the prevalent thinking style among all criminal thinking styles of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL), which indicates that most of the Davao City Jail offenders consider failure as a circumstance where they are not at fault and place the blame on other factors. As well as, study shows that the manifestation of criminal thinking styles of Davao City Jail Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) is moderate in terms of mollification, cutoff, entitlement, sentimentality, super optimism, cognitive indolence, and discontinuity, which indicates that these thinking are present in all offenders. At the same time, the power orientation thinking style was the lowest among the respondents. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant difference among all of the criminal thinking styles in terms of gender.

The result also shows that most of the inmates at the Davao City Jail are convicted of drug-related crimes and have a typical criminal thinking style of super optimism. It would lead to a low level of power orientation thinking style because this kind of criminal thinking style is common in offenders who are charged with murder (Megreya et al., 2015).Based on the conclusion, the following suggestions were made:

The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology must ensure that their facilities have a psychologist who will provide and oversee programs to lower recidivism rates and offer regular counseling to all prisoners. However, punishment is not the only purpose of prison. Prison is frequently about rehabilitation as well. Most prisoners will be freed and reintegrated into society. Prisons need psychologists to assist inmates in their reintegration into society. Various psychological interventions have been applied in imprisonment settings to enhance outcomes for those released from jail and, specifically, to lower reoffending. Based on the meta-analyses, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) programs reduce recidivism risk by 20–30%, according to specific reviews, making it one of the most effective interventions (Beaudry et al., 2021).For the benefit of potential researchers in the future, finding more respondents on other criminal offenses might be a great addition. Most of the results are being gathered from offenders with drug-related cases; respondents with other criminal offenses will let them dig for more profound information about their thinking style. Future work should aim to assess the other offenders with other criminal offenses to know what prevalent criminal thinking styles lie in them. This study can benefit the correctional staff, law enforcement, and the community. Understanding how lawbreakers behave would let them develop some programs and interventions for the treatment of the offenders inside the institution. Helping offenders in the correctional facility manage their thinking style might greatly help reduce recidivism when they are released. It is an opportunity for both sides to have a productive common ground. The authorities can upgrade their way of supervision, rehabilitation, and custodial of criminal offenders.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to express their sincerest gratitude to the following people who made this paper possible. First and foremost, we want to thank our parents for their sacrifices, endless love, and support, and our Lord Jesus Christ for providing us with a mentor and equipping us with the knowledge, courage, and optimistic perspective we need to finish this study.

To our Dear Research Adviser, **Irish P. Bandolos, MSCJ**, thank you so much for helping us and ensuring we understood everything needed to finish this research. In particular, we appreciate you being there for us each time we had questions about our research paper, which helped us complete this research.

To our beloved Dean, **Dr. Carmelita B Chavez**, we thank you for sparing time to sign our letters as needed for our research paper.

To our dearest statistician **Joey C. Oliveros, MAed**, thank you for taking the time to interpret our study's results and guiding us to understand it.

To **JO1 Chardyl Plana** and **JCSUPT Peter D. Bonggat Jr.**, thank you for your approval for us to be able to conduct our survey questionnaires inside the jail facility.

To our Dear Panelists, **Dr. Nestor C. Nabe** and **Dr. Roberto R. Magbojos**, thank you for your time and effort in giving suggestions that we needed.

REFERENCES

- [1.] *Effectiveness of psychological interventions in prison to reduce recidivism: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials— ScienceDirect.* (n.d.). Retrieved October 19, 2022, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221503662100170X>
- [2.] Escrig-Espuig, J. M., Martí-Vilar, M., & González-Sala, F. (2022). Criminal Thinking: Exploring its Relationship with Prosocial Behavior, Emotional Intelligence, and Cultural Dimensions. *Anuario de Psicología Jurídica.* <https://doi.org/10.5093/apj2022a2>
- [3.] Gasco, L. D. (n.d.). *Artists and crooks: A correlational examination of creativity and criminal thinking.* 131..
- [4.] *General Strain Theory | Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology.* (n.d.). Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <https://oxfordre.com/criminology/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264079-e-249>
- [5.] *General Strain Theory | Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology.* (n.d.). Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <https://oxfordre.com/criminology/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264079-e-249>
- [6.] Herman, J. (2015). *Trauma and recovery.* New York: Basic Books.
- [7.] Hulsey, T. (n.d.). *The PICTS, Trauma, Experiential Avoidance, Criminal Thinking and Behavior in an Online Community Sample.* 125. (*The PICTS, Trauma, Experiential Avoidance, Criminal Thinking and Behavior in an Online Community Sample - UNT Digital Library*, n.d.) Pawar, N. (2020). 6. *Type of Research and Type Research Design* (pp. 46– 57).
- [8.] *Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles (Forensic Psychology) IResearchNet.* (n.d.). Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <http://criminal-justice.iresearchnet.com/forensic-psychology/psychological-inventory-of-criminal-thinking-styles/>
- [9.] Pepper, S. (2012). *The role of experiential avoidance in trauma, substance abuse, and other experiences.* (Unpublished Dissertation). Denton, T

- [10.] (PDF) *The use of the Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles with English young offenders* | Clive Hollin—Academia.edu. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2022, from
- [11.] https://www.academia.edu/22844910/The_use_of_the_Psychological_Inventory_of_Criminal_Thinking_Styles_with_English_young_offenders?fbclid=IwAR3gHHkIagDLucFod8d_akx8Xx32i_y6Xa0K_Bkj6qa-5on96sc1sfmu1Zc
- [12.] (PDF) *Gender Differences in the Measurement of Criminal Thinking* | ResearchGate. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310466861_Gender_Differences_in_the_Measurement_of_Criminal_Thinking?fbclid=IwAR3VfOR_8uo_BwwAWGgcmYtnLwbzT0Bu0Gib9ci73_pHKnqjG7e2x9RG_Uw
- [13.] *The Criminal's Belief System*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2022, from https://www.theraponiversity.org/cbs/cbs_20.html?fbclid=IwAR2_PJXhx20q7zdigr1AjJxLbHiGR61qv_dZ4JF6qsMaD0dIHOxL3ktV4CSw
- [14.] *The Criminal's "Superoptimism"* | *Psychology Today*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2022, from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/inside-the-criminal->
- [15.] *Reliability, Validity, and Predictive Utility of the 25-Item Criminogenic Cognitions Scale (CCS)*—PMC. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2022, from https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3779895/?fbclid=IwAR3gHv5CS_SV6U9UI6L7ivS_wuGjHyfeZWVx7HzrpTBnBxV5teImGCh6r2rg
- [16.] Vrućinić, Ž. (2019). The difference in criminal thinking styles and the depth of involvement in criminal lifestyles with regard to the age, recidivism, and violence of a criminal offense. *Nauka Bezbednost Policija*, 24(3), 79–95. <https://doi.org/10.5937/nabepo24-20558>
- [17.] Walters, G. (1995). The Psychological Inventory of Criminal Thinking Styles. Part I: Reliability 120 and preliminary validity. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 22, 307-325.
- [18.] Walters, G. (2001). Psychological Index of Criminal Thinking Styles (Version 4.0).
- [19.] Walters, G. (2002). Current and Historical content scales for the Psychological Index of Criminal Thinking Styles (PICTS). *Legal & Criminological Psychology*, 7(1), 73, 14.
- [20.] *What is Non-Probability Sampling in 2022?* - Qualtrics. (n.d.). Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/research/non-probability-sampling/>